

4 Poems by Lidia Chiarelli

Lights in the Rock Garden (Torino “ville lumière”)

*“The footpath lights in the garden were hidden by ferns and roses,
giving the area a muted green glow, almost like being under the sea.”*

— Sarah Addison Allen, *Other Birds: A Novel*

Darkness surrounded me.
At the distance
echoes came in subtle vibrations
in a slow crescendo
a gloomy, confused whisper...

Then the lights switched on
in the garden of a thousand colours.
They switched on vibrant and warm
on the water of fountains
on the petals of roses
caressed by the April breeze.
As I walked
on the flowered paths
subtle fragrances
wrapped me up in the deep silence.

Legacy of magic memories
that every night come back alive
again and again
in my beautiful Turin, “ville lumière”.

(in memory of my father, Guido Chiarelli, pioneer of public lighting)

WHERE DREAMS DWELL

So tremulously like a dream ...
 (“Clown in the moon” - Dylan Thomas)

In a separate world
dreams are alive.
Constellations of lights and
interstellar sounds attend their birth.
They creep into our minds
through a meandering trail
when the night is darkest.
Like dancing shadows
tremulous they enter
they play, mutate, dominate

are lost in dissociated sequences.
They plunge into the unfathomable
depths of memory
to emerge again.
And when the first blades of light
pierce the sky
they vanish ... crumpled, shattered
toward invisible horizons
in echoing silence

WINTER SUNSETS

*that bit of light in a moment slips away
(from: Ray of Sun, Ko Un - South Korea)*

The short winter sunsets
take promises of light

when the last hour of the day
is lost
between rarefied gauzes of mist.

Fans of lighted clouds
on the horizon
fleeing
where the sky ends.

View from the Cliff

Portovenere, La Spezia, August 2025

*A heap of broken images, where the sun beats,
And the dead tree gives no shelter...
(T.S. Eliot: The Waste Land)*

Here where gray blends with blue
where small waves melt into blades of light
even the rough voice of the sea
slowly disappears.

Water and clouds float in slow transition
and we are waiting
for the evening shadows and
for a cool breeze that will not come.

In front of us a heap of broken images :

while the late hours of this too-hot day
inexorably get lost in a dark labyrinth.

In the distance the tide's ebb and flow
whisper the last call to save the earth.

Bio:

Lidia Chiarelli (Torino, Italy). Artist and writer, co-founder of the art-literary Movement **Immagine & Poesia** (2007). Award-winning poet. Her poems are translated in more than 20 languages and published in literary magazines and on websites of different countries. Literary Art Medal, NY 2020.

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